

Investigating the Interactome of
***Arabidopsis thaliana* MPKs**
An Integrative Approach Using Multiple Sources
of Evidence and Machine Learning-Based
Structural Modeling

by
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Abstract

The *Arabidopsis thaliana* mitogen-activated protein kinase (MPK) signaling network plays a role in various cellular processes. This study integrated protein-protein interaction, genetic interaction, and co-expression data from the STRING, BioGRID, and ATTED-II databases to provide a comprehensive dataset of interactions within the network. The key MPK network components from this set were identified and subjected to functional enrichment analysis, which revealed their involvement in diverse biological processes and pathways. The 3D structure of MKK2 was predicted using AlphaFold2, and protein-protein docking simulations were performed between MPK6 and MKK2. The docking analysis identified important residues mediating their interaction. This integrative approach, combining multiple sources of evidence, structural predictions, and protein-protein docking, provides a comprehensive approach for understanding the *A. thaliana* MPK signaling network. The findings demonstrate the complex regulatory mechanisms that play a role in plant stress responses and development.

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Chapter 1

General Introduction

1.1 *Arabidopsis thaliana* as a Model Organism

1.1.1 General Characteristics

Arabidopsis thaliana has emerged as a powerful model organism in plant biology research due to its numerous advantages. *A. thaliana* shares developmental, reproductive, and stress response similarities with many crop plants, making it an ideal model for studying these processes (Mishra et al., 2019). The plant's small and fully sequenced genome, short regeneration time, and modest growth requirements have greatly facilitated genetic and molecular analyses (Ausubel, 2018; B. Keurentjes et al., 2008; Krämer, 2015; Pitzschke, 2013). These characteristics have allowed researchers to fully utilize molecular biology tools and methods, leading to significant advancements in understanding the molecular principles of plant development, cell biology, metabolism, physiology, genetics, and epigenetics (Krämer, 2015; Somssich, 2022).

Moreover, *A. thaliana* has served as a highly productive research organism for exploring fundamental biology, with direct applications to human health. Studies on DNA repair, photobiology, protein degradation, the circadian clock, DNA methylation, RNA silencing, and G-protein signaling in *A. thaliana* have provided valuable insights into these processes (Lamesch et al., 2011). The availability of extensive genetic resources and the success in creating transgenic plants have further contributed to the efficiency of *A. thaliana* as a model plant for plant physiology and molecular biology research (Pitzschke, 2013; Yahya, 2022).

1.1.2 Contributions for Understanding Plant Stress Response

A. thaliana has played a crucial role in highlighting the molecular mechanisms underlying plant stress responses. Research using this model organism has shed light on the initial transcriptional stress reaction, which comprises a set of core environmental stress response genes that are crucial in various stress responses (Kilian et al., 2007). These findings have contributed to the identification of key players in molecular mechanisms mediating complex stress responses in plants, paving the way for the development of improved stress-tolerant crops (Shameer et al., 2009).

Arabidopsis has been instrumental in investigating the roles of various proteins and signaling pathways in plant stress responses. For example, studies on small heat shock proteins (sHSPs) and voltage-dependent anion channel 2 (AtVDAC2) in *A. thaliana* have provided insights into heavy metal resistance and salicylic acid and salt stress response mechanisms, respectively (Cui et al., 2019; Liu et al., 2015). Expression profiling in *A. thaliana* has also been utilized to exploit conserved stress-signaling networks for improving stress tolerance in crops (Zeller et al., 2009).

Furthermore, research on *A. thaliana* has revealed the involvement of various hormones and signaling molecules in plant stress responses. Studies have highlighted the role of gibberellins in salicylic acid-modulated early plant responses to abiotic stress (Alonso-Ramírez et al., 2009) and the antagonism between salicylic and abscisic acid in shaping plant defense responses (Torres Zabala et al., 2009). The coordination of stress-induced hormone signaling pathways by Arabidopsis BAG genes has also been investigated, contributing to the understanding of stress response mechanisms (Doukhanina et al., 2006).

In addition to these specific findings, *A. thaliana* has been used to develop valuable resources for studying plant stress responses, such as the Arabidopsis Stress Responsive Gene Database (Borkotoky et al., 2013) and the identification of stress-regulated microRNAs (Liu et al., 2008; Mishra et al., 2009). These resources have greatly facilitated the understanding of plant stress responses at the molecular level.

Overall, the use of *A. thaliana* as a model organism has significantly advanced our understanding of plant stress responses, providing valuable insights into the molecular mechanisms, signaling pathways, and regulatory networks involved in these processes. These findings have laid the foundation for the development of strategies to improve stress tolerance in crop plants, thereby contributing to global food security in the face of changing environmental conditions.

1.2 MPK Signaling

1.2.1 Overview of MPK Signaling Cascades

Mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) cascades are highly conserved signal transduction pathways that play crucial roles in regulating plant growth, development, and stress responses (Im et al., 2021; Mohanta et al., 2015; Popescu et al., 2008). These signaling pathways consist of three main components: MPK kinase kinases (MAPKKKs), MPK kinases (MKKs), and MPKs, which are activated through sequential phosphorylation events in response to various extracellular and intracellular signals (Lee et al., 2008a; Popescu et al., 2008).

MPK signaling cascades are central to the amplification and transduction of signals generated by receptors, and they are involved in a wide range of plant processes, including development, cell proliferation, and responses to biotic and abiotic stresses (Hu et al., 2018; Lampard et al., 2008; Lee et al., 2008a; Zhang et al., 2007). The MPK signaling pathway transfers signals from the cell membrane to the nucleus, regulating the corresponding gene expression (Im et al., 2021). Emerging evidence suggests that MPK signaling pathways are connected with many aspects of plant development and are also activated in response to stresses, promoting stress tolerance in plants (Jia et al., 2016; Kim et al., 2022).

1.2.2 Components of MPK Signaling Cascades

The three main components of MPK signaling pathways, MAPKKKs, MKKs, and MPKs, work together to transduce signals and regulate various plant processes.

MAPKKKs are involved in diverse signaling pathways triggered by hormone treatments or abiotic stresses, and their functional characterization has highlighted their diverse roles in developmental, tissue, and signal-dependent contexts (Li et al., 2016; Wang et al., 2014; Zhang et al., 2018). MKKs, which are activated in response to various extracellular stimuli, phosphorylate MPKs. For instance, the MKK7-MPK3/6 module is involved in regulating plant development and plant basal and systemic immune responses (Huck et al., 2017). MPKs, the final component of the cascade, are important signaling molecules that regulate plant growth, development, and stress responses by conducting phosphorylation events in their target proteins (Mohanta et al., 2015).

1.2.3 Role of MPK Signaling in Plant Stress Response

MPK signaling pathways play a critical role in plant stress responses, particularly in response to abiotic stresses such as salt stress. MPKs are activated in response to stresses and promote stress tolerance in plants (Kim et al., 2022; Zhai et al., 2022). In the context of salt stress, the nuclear translocation of MPK6 is mediated by hydrogen peroxide (Im et al., 2021), and the roles of phospholipase D α (PLD α) and phosphatidic acid in mediating salt stress signaling through the regulation of MPKs have been studied (Yu et al., 2010). Traditional genetic and biochemical methods have identified MAPKKK/MKK/MPK signaling modules with overlapping roles in controlling cell division, development, hormone signaling and synthesis, and response to abiotic stress and pathogens (Popescu et al., 2008).

In summary, MPK signaling pathways, consisting of MAPKKKs, MKKs, and MPKs, are essential for regulating plant growth, development, and stress responses. These highly conserved cascades transduce signals through sequential phosphorylation events, enabling plants to respond to various extracellular and intracellular stimuli. The role of MPK signaling in plant stress responses, particularly in response to abiotic stresses such as salt stress, highlights the importance of these pathways in promoting plant stress tolerance.

1.3 Omics and Systems Biology

1.3.1 Proteomics and Protein-Protein Interactions

Proteomics involves the systematic analysis and characterization of proteins within a cell, tissue, or organism. This approach has been instrumental in understanding plant responses to various pathogens and environmental stresses (Petersen et al., 2013).

Protein-protein interactions (PPIs) play an important role in plant biology, providing insights into the regulation of plant developmental, physiological, and pathological processes (Zhang et al., 2010). The application of proteomics in progressing insights into plant secondary metabolism and stress responses has been a subject of interest, highlighting the importance of proteomics in understanding the dynamic nature of the plant proteome (Martínez-Esteso et al., 2015; Ngara and Ndimba, 2014).

1.3.2 Genomics and Genetic Interactions

Genomics involves the comprehensive study of the genetic material of plants, encompassing their entire DNA sequence, gene expression patterns, and genetic interactions. The field of genomics has significantly advanced through the integration of new technologies, algorithms, and approaches, providing deep insights into plant biology (Hamilton and Buell, 2012).

Genetic interactions refer to the ways in which different genes or genetic elements interact with each other to produce a particular phenotype, and understanding these interactions is important for exploring plant biology, including plant-insect interactions, evolutionary processes, and the development of new genetic engineering techniques (Gompert et al., 2019; Yu et al., 2018).

1.3.3 Transcriptomics and Gene Co-Expression

Transcriptomics involves the study of the complete set of RNA transcripts produced by the genome under specific circumstances or in a specific cell using high-throughput methods. It provides comprehensive insights into gene expression patterns, alternative splicing, and post-transcriptional modifications, thereby contributing to a deeper understanding of plant biology (Best et al., 2020).

Gene co-expression, a concept derived from transcriptomics, refers to the phenomenon where the expression levels of two or more genes show a significant correlation across a set of samples or conditions. Co-expression networks have been instrumental in identifying gene modules involved in specific biological processes, such as host plant selection, development, and stress responses (Liang et al., 2014; Tian et al., 2021; Tran et al., 2013).

1.3.4 Multi-Omics Data Integration

The integration of multi-omics data has become an important component of systems biology, allowing for a comprehensive understanding of the molecular mechanisms underlying plant biology (Katam et al., 2022). This integrated approach provides insights into complex biological processes, such as plant responses to environmental stimuli, interactions with other organisms, and the identification of potential traits for crop improvement (Meena et al., 2017). The integration of omics datasets has led to the discovery of different plant stress response mechanisms and has improved our understanding of plant biological processes (Cramer et al., 2011; Zhou et al., 2022).

Overall, the application of omics technologies and systems biology approaches has significantly enhanced the study of plant biology, providing a comprehensive understanding of plant systems. The integration of proteomics, genomics, transcriptomics, and their associated interactions has led to significant advancements in our understanding of plant responses to environmental stimuli, interactions with other organisms, and the identification of potential traits for crop improvement. As the field of plant biology continues to evolve, the integration of multi-omics data will play an increasingly important role in unraveling the complexity of plant systems and driving new discoveries in this field.

1.4 Structural Biology and Protein Function

1.4.1 Role of Structural Biology in Protein Function

Structural biology plays an important role in understanding the regulatory mechanisms and functional implications of protein phosphorylation in plants. Phosphorylation, a post-translational modification, is a key regulator of various biological processes in plants, including responses to biotic and abiotic stresses, growth, development, and signal transduction (Chen et al., 2015). The study of phosphorylation sites and their dynamics is essential for comprehending the conformational sampling of phosphorylated proteins, particularly in intrinsically disordered proteins, which are prevalent in plant biology (Zhong et al., 2022). Large-scale comparative phosphoproteomics studies have identified conserved phosphorylation sites in plants, providing evidence for conserved regulatory mechanisms (Nakagami et al., 2010). These findings underscore the significance of structural biology in unraveling the conservation and diversity of phosphorylation events in plant proteins and their impact on essential cellular processes (Al-Momani et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2016).

For instance, the integrated database for plant protein phosphorylation (P3DB) serves as a valuable resource for exploring the relationship between protein phosphorylation and disorder analysis (Yao et al., 2012). Quantitative phosphoproteomic studies have shed light on the regulatory role of phosphorylation in plant defense mechanisms and the influence of specific stimuli on plant responses to environmental cues (Fan et al., 2014; Hou et al., 2016).

1.4.2 Advances in Protein Structure Prediction

Recent advances in protein structure prediction, particularly with the emergence of AlphaFold2, have revolutionized the field of computational biology and protein research. AlphaFold2, a deep learning-based approach, has demonstrated remarkable success in accurately predicting protein structures (Pakhrin et al., 2021). The accuracy of AlphaFold2 has been reported to be close to that of experimental determination techniques, signifying a significant leap in the reliability of predicted protein structures (Wang et al., 2022).

AlphaFold2 has enhanced the understanding of protein interactions and has shown promise in discriminating protein-protein interactions (Martin, 2024). The combination of AlphaFold2 with other modeling approaches has led to improved success rates in protein structure prediction and docking (Ghani et al., 2021). The emergence of AlphaFold2 has paved the way for the convergence of structural bioinformatics and artificial intelligence, with ongoing efforts to establish standardized models for protein structure prediction (Szelogowski, 2023).

1.4.3 Modeling Interaction Interfaces with Protein-Protein Docking

Protein-protein docking plays an important role in modeling interaction interfaces in the context of plant biology, as it allows for the prediction of the protein complex structure and identification of key interaction residues. HADDOCK, a tool for protein-protein docking, utilizes experimental knowledge to drive the docking process, allowing for predictions in various protein interaction scenarios (Trellet et al., 2013).

In plant biology, protein-protein docking techniques have been instrumental in studying various interactions, including those involving peptides and short linear motif fragments. The CABS-dock method has been utilized to accurately model specific interactions (Ciemny et al., 2017). The application of protein-protein docking has also extended to the prediction of protein-protein interaction structures using evolutionary information, as exemplified by the InterEvDock server (Yu et al., 2016). Additionally, protein-protein docking has been utilized to study the interaction of plant proteins with other organisms, contributing to the understanding of host-pathogen interactions and plant immunity (Peyraud et al., 2017).

1.5 Functional Annotation and Pathway Mapping

1.5.1 Functional Annotation for Biological Processes

Functional annotation is a crucial step in understanding the roles of genes and their products in various cellular activities and biological processes in plants. It involves associating gene products with specific biological processes, molecular functions, and cellular components, placing sequencing data in a meaningful biological context (Bargsten et al., 2014; Lohse et al., 2013; Schwacke et al., 2019). Functional annotation is a multi-layered process that utilizes ontologies such as the Gene Ontology (GO) to describe gene products in terms of their associated functions, components, and processes (Ghelfi et al., 2018; Shi et al., 2014). This process is essential for connecting genome data to plant biology and facilitating the understanding of gene functions in the context of biological systems.

Functional annotation is not limited to protein-coding genes but also extends to non-coding RNAs, where comprehensive annotation is crucial for understanding their roles in plant biology (Leroy et al., 2012; Paytuví-Gallart et al., 2015). Moreover, the computational prediction and functional annotation of miRNA target genes play a significant role in highlighting the specific biological functions of miRNAs (Pio et al., 2012). In the context of systems biology, functional annotation is considered a fundamental step for modeling and analyzing functional genomics data, ensuring accurate representation of gene functions in species with recently sequenced genomes (Berg et al., 2010).

1.5.2 Approaches to Functional Annotation and Pathway Mapping

Various approaches have been developed to facilitate functional annotation and pathway mapping in plant biology, leveraging integrated data sources, computational tools, and genomic resources. Systems biology approaches provide a comprehensive understanding of plant responses to abiotic stress by identifying key biological pathways involved (Cramer, 2010). High-throughput comparison, functional annotation, and metabolic modeling of plant genomes using resources such as PlantSEED enable the mapping of reactions in biochemical pathways to biological functions, supporting genome annotation and curation (Seaver et al., 2014).

Integrative approaches, such as the combination of genome annotation and quantitative trait loci (QTL) positions, have been utilized to identify candidate genes for

productivity, architecture, and water-use efficiency in plants (Monclus et al., 2012). Semantic similarity measures have also been proposed for integrating Gene Ontology annotations from different pipelines, enhancing the integration of heterogeneous data for functional annotation (Mazandu and Mulder, 2014). Computational tools for designing and testing plant synthetic metabolic pathways highlight the potential for metabolic engineering in plant biology (Küken and Nikoloski, 2019), while the use of synthetic biology in plastids leverages their amenability to large-scale genome manipulations for both top-down and bottom-up approaches (Scharff and Bock, 2013).

1.5.3 Available Databases and Resources

Numerous databases and resources are available for functional annotation and pathway information in plant biology. The Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes (KEGG) is a comprehensive database that integrates genomic, chemical, and systemic functional information, providing pathway maps and cross-referenced information for various organisms (Tanabe and Kanehisa, 2012; Wrzodek et al., 2013). KEGG pathway analysis has been instrumental in identifying metabolic pathways, biosynthesis of secondary metabolites, plant-pathogen interactions, and plant hormone signal transduction (Singh et al., 2021).

The Gene Ontology (GO) database provides a standardized vocabulary for describing the molecular functions, biological processes, and cellular components of gene products, with cross-references to other databases (Wan et al., 2012). WikiPathways is a collaborative platform for curated pathway information, allowing researchers to contribute and maintain biological pathways relevant to plant biology (Seaver et al., 2014).

Specialized plant biology databases such as the Arabidopsis Information Resource (TAIR) and PlantMetabolomics.org offer essential information for the plant biology community. TAIR serves as a community database for Arabidopsis researchers (Lamesch et al., 2011), while PlantMetabolomics.org is a web portal and database for exploring, visualizing, and downloading plant metabolomics data (Bais et al., 2010).

The integration of multiple functional annotation tools has been shown to increase the coverage of metabolic annotation, emphasizing the importance of combining diverse resources for comprehensive functional annotation (Griesemer et al., 2017). These databases and resources play a vital role in understanding gene functions, biological pathways, and molecular interactions in plants, contributing to the advancement of plant biology research.

1.6 Current Research Gaps

Despite the extensive research on MPK signaling pathways in plants, several research gaps need to be addressed:

- Some MPKs in model plants including *A. thaliana* have not been fully characterized, which limits our understanding of their specific biological functions and roles in stress response pathways.
- The functions of many MAPKKK genes, which are critical upstream activators of MPK signaling cascades, are still unclear. This prevents us from having a comprehensive understanding of their contributions to plant stress responses and the downstream targets they regulate.
- Although physical interactions between components of MPK signaling cascades have been identified in *A. thaliana*, the structural aspects of these interactions have been less studied, limiting our knowledge of the molecular mechanisms and structural basis of signal transduction in these pathways.

1.7 Research Objectives

To address the current research gaps and advance our understanding of MPK signaling in plants, this thesis aims to:

- Construct a dataset by integrating various types of omics data, including protein-protein interactions (PPI), genetic interactions, and gene co-expression, to explore the MPK signaling network in *Arabidopsis thaliana* and identify novel signaling pathways that may play important roles in plant stress responses.
- Analyze the key components of the MPK signaling network and highlight their specific roles in stress response and signal transduction through functional annotation and pathway enrichment analyses, providing a more comprehensive understanding of the molecular mechanisms underlying plant stress responses.
- Predict the three-dimensional structure of MKK2, an important upstream activator of MPK6 in cold and salt stress signaling, using AlphaFold2, and perform protein-protein docking simulations with MPK6 to identify key residues involved in their interaction, contributing to a better understanding of the structural basis of MPK signaling in plants.

Chapter 2

Exploratory Study of the *Arabidopsis* MPK Network

2.1 Introduction

The *Arabidopsis thaliana* mitogen-activated protein kinase (MPK) signaling network plays an important role in various cellular processes, including stress response and development. To identify both known and potentially novel MPK interactions in, this exploratory study involved the construction of a comprehensive dataset using a systematic and integrative approach. The focus of this research was essential for achieving the objectives, as it laid the foundation for understanding the complex interactions within the MPK network and guided the investigations detailed in the subsequent chapters.

The dataset was constructed through a systematic process involving the retrieval, processing, and integration of data from multiple source databases, each providing a different type of evidence, such as protein-protein interactions, genetic interactions, and gene co-expression. The retrieved data was then ranked based on the number of evidence sources supporting each interaction, allowing for the prioritization of interactions and selection of key MPK network components for further analysis.

The results of this study provide a comprehensive overview of the *A. thaliana* MPK interactome, revealing both known interactions supported by experimental evidence and predicted interactions, which warrant further investigation. The findings inform the analyses conducted in the subsequent chapters, with the functional genomics analysis of the predicted MPK interactions discussed in Chapter 3. Additionally, the known MKK2-MPK6 physical interaction emerged as an interaction of interest and was further studied through structural modeling and molecular docking in Chapters 4

and 5, respectively. By using this systematic and integrative approach to explore the MPK interactome, this exploratory study established a solid foundation for subsequent investigations and contributes to the overall understanding of the complex regulatory mechanisms underlying plant stress responses and development.

2.2 Materials and Methods

2.2.1 Retrieval of Protein-Protein Interaction Data

The STRING Database

Protein-protein interaction data were obtained from the STRING database (version 12.0) using its application programming interface (API). STRING is an extensive resource that integrates both known and predicted protein-protein interactions, including physical interactions and functional associations. The database collects and scores evidence from various sources, such as automated text mining, experiments, computational predictions, and systematic transfers of interaction evidence across organisms. STRING assesses and transfers this information to less-well-studied organisms using hierarchical orthology (Szklarczyk et al., 2011, 2019, 2023).

Data Collection and Processing

For each of the 20 MPKs of *Arabidopsis thaliana*, we conducted a query in STRING, specifying the species using the NCBI Taxonomic ID 3702. The network type parameter was set to the Functional Network, which represents the Full STRING Network and consists of both physical and functional associations. The minimum required score was set at a medium confidence score of 0.4. The maximum number of interactions to retrieve for each MPK was set at 500 to obtain a wide range of interactions. The query parameters used for data collection are outlined in Table 1.

Table 2.1 Parameters for Data Retrieval from STRING.

Parameter	Value
Species Taxonomic ID	3702 (<i>A. thaliana</i>)
Network Type	Functional (Full STRING Network)
Minimum Required Score	0.400 (Medium Confidence)
Maximum Number of Interactions	500

Following the retrieval of individual files, the data were consolidated into a single comprehensive file to simplify integration with subsequent genetic interaction and gene co-expression data. This consolidation process involved merging individual files and ensuring that the data were properly formatted and compatible for further analysis.

2.2.2 Retrieval of Genetic Interaction Data

The BioGRID Database

Genetic interactions for the MPKs were obtained from BioGRID (version 4.4.232) using the API. BioGRID is a database that curates protein and genetic interactions in various species, including *A. thaliana*, based on primary experimental evidence from scientific literature. This ensures the high quality and reliability of the interactions in the database. BioGRID consists of both low-throughput studies and high-throughput datasets (Oughtred et al., 2020, 2018; Stark, 2006), and allows for a comprehensive overview of genetic interactions.

Data Collection and Processing

Each MPK was individually queried using BioGRID, with the NCBI Taxonomic ID set to 3702 for *A. thaliana*. The obtained data were then filtered to include only genetic interactions, as our focus was on understanding the genetic relationships between MPKs and other genes.

The individual files were subsequently combined into a comprehensive file, retaining certain columns and eliminating others based on their relevance to the analysis. This process involved carefully selecting columns that contained essential information for our study and removing any irrelevant data. By doing so, we streamlined the dataset and prepared it for integration with the protein-protein interaction and gene co-expression data.

2.2.3 Retrieval of Gene Co-Expression Data

The ATTED-II Database

To obtain gene co-expression data for *A. thaliana* MPKs, we accessed the ATTED-II database (version 11.1) using the API. ATTED-II is a comprehensive resource that integrates RNA sequencing and microarray data from *A. thaliana* and other plant species to predict gene functions and interactions. This resource identifies genes with

similar expression profiles, suggesting functional relationships or joint roles in cellular processes (Obayashi et al., 2018, 2022).

The ATTED-II database utilizes principal component analysis (PCA) and ensemble calculations for sample balancing, which improves the quality of the co-expression data. Each gene pair in the database is assigned a metric called the Logit Score, which serves as an indicator of the strength of their co-expression relationship (Obayashi et al., 2018, 2022). A higher Logit Score suggests a stronger co-expression relationship between the gene pair, implying a closer functional association. Conversely, a lower Logit Score indicates a weaker co-expression relationship, suggesting a less significant functional association.

Data Collection and Processing

To collect co-expression data for the MPKs, we queried the ATTED-II database using the API. The query parameters were set to retrieve co-expression relationships based on the "Ath-u.c3-0" platform. Additionally, we limited the number of co-expressed genes retrieved for each MPK to 200.

After retrieving the co-expression data from ATTED-II, we processed the data to prepare it for integration with the protein-protein interaction and genetic interaction data. This processing step involved formatting the data, ensuring consistency in gene identifiers, and removing duplicate or irrelevant entries. By cleaning and organizing the co-expression data, we ensured its compatibility with other datasets and facilitated the subsequent integration and analysis steps.

2.2.4 Integration and Ranking of Data

Integration of Data

To gain a comprehensive understanding of the potential interactors of MPKs in *A. thaliana*, we integrated PPI data from the STRING database, genetic interaction data from the BioGRID database, and gene co-expression data from the ATTED-II database to construct a comprehensive dataset. Each of these data sources provided a specific type of evidence supporting the potential interactions between MPKs and predicted interactors.

The integration process involved combining the three datasets based on common gene identifiers. By merging these datasets, we created a unified resource that captures the diverse types of interactions and relationships between MPKs and other genes in *A.*

thaliana. This integrated dataset served as the foundation for our subsequent analysis and prioritization of potential MPK interactors.

Ranking and Prioritization Strategy

To prioritize the relevant MPK interactions in the dataset, we used a ranking strategy that considered the presence of multiple sources of evidence supporting each interaction. This method allowed us to assign a higher degree of confidence to interactions supported by multiple sources. The ranking and prioritization strategies implemented are as follows:

- **Rank 1:** Interactions supported by all three sources of evidence (PPIs from STRING, genetic interactions from BioGRID, and gene co-expression from ATTED-II) were ranked highest. These interactions were considered the most reliable, as they were consistently observed across different sources of evidence.
- **Rank 2:** Interactions supported by two of the three sources of evidence were ranked lower than those supported by all three; however, they were still higher than the interactions supported by only one source of evidence.
- **Rank 3:** Interactions supported by only a single source of evidence were ranked the lowest among all interactions. Although these interactions were considered potentially relevant, they were assigned a lower confidence level than those supported by multiple sources of evidence.

Selection of Key MPK Network Components

After ranking the interactions, we further refined the dataset by selecting the interaction pairs with at least two sources of evidence. This criterion ensured that the selected interactions had a higher level of confidence and were supported by multiple experimental or computational approaches.

To focus on the most critical components of the MPK network, we further narrowed down the dataset to include only key interactions. This selection process involved considering factors such as the biological relevance of the interacting partners, their known functions, and their potential roles in MPK signaling pathways. By concentrating on these key components, we aimed to identify the most essential and influential interactions within the MPK network.

Following the selection of these key interactions, a literature search was conducted to determine whether they were already known or predicted. The results of this literature

search were categorized into two groups: known interactions supported by experimental evidence and predicted interactions that had not been experimentally validated. This categorization provided valuable insights into the current state of knowledge regarding MPK interactions and highlighted potential novel interactions that warrant further investigation.

2.3 Results

2.3.1 Integrated Dataset of MPK Interactions

The integration of protein-protein interaction data from STRING, genetic interaction data from BioGRID, and gene co-expression data from ATTED-II resulted in a comprehensive dataset containing potential interactors of *Arabidopsis thaliana* MPKs. The final dataset contains the Number of Sources (num_sources), Source Databases (source_db), STRING Score (string_score), ATTED Logit Score (atted_ls), and BioGRID Genetic Evidence Type (biogrid_evidence) for each interaction. For interactions where a specific field was not applicable, it was marked as "N/A". The dataset has can be found in the supplementary materials.

2.3.2 Selected MPK Network Components

The criteria for selecting the MPK network interactions for further analysis were based on the requirement of having a minimum of two sources of evidence and interactors being upstream of MPKs. These selected interactions include the following:

- MKK2-MPK4
- MKK1-MPK1
- MKK1-MPK2
- MKK2-MPK2
- MKK4-MPK3
- MKK9-MPK3
- MEKK1-MPK3
- MKK1-MPK4

- MKK2-MPK6
- MKK5-MPK6
- YDA-MPK9
- MKK1-MPK11
- MKK6-MPK13
- MEKK1-MPK17

Table 1 presents the selected interactions, displaying the STRING Score, ATTED Logit Score, and BioGRID Genetic Evidence Type for each interaction.

Table 2.2 Selected Subset of Upstream MPK Interactions with Multiple Sources of Evidence

MPK	Interactor	Number of Sources	Source	STRING Score	ATTED Logit Score	BioGRID Evidence Type
MPK4	MKK2	3	STRING, BioGRID, ATTED	0.993	4.9821	Synthetic Rescue
MPK1	MKK1	2	STRING, ATTED	0.693	3.344	N/A
MPK2	MKK1	2	STRING, ATTED	0.700	3.5388	N/A
MPK2	MKK2	2	STRING, ATTED	0.659	5.1195	N/A
MPK3	MKK4	2	STRING, ATTED	0.990	4.6728	N/A
MPK3	MKK9	2	STRING, ATTED	0.970	4.4093	N/A
MPK3	MEKK1	2	STRING, ATTED	0.705	3.6991	N/A
MPK4	MKK1	2	STRING, ATTED	0.996	3.8939	N/A
MPK6	MKK2	2	STRING, BioGRID	0.992	N/A	Synthetic Rescue
MPK6	MKK5	2	STRING, ATTED	0.991	3.8137	N/A
MPK9	YDA	2	STRING, ATTED	0.406	2.9775	N/A
MPK11	MKK1	2	STRING, ATTED	0.88	4.7415	N/A
MPK13	MKK6	2	STRING, ATTED	0.942	4.9706	N/A
MPK17	MEKK1	2	STRING, ATTED	0.459	3.0577	N/A

2.3.3 Experimental Evidence and Computational Predictions

A literature search was conducted to categorize the selected interactions as either known interactions with supporting experimental evidence or computationally predicted interactions lacking experimental validation.

Experimentally Validated Interactions

The interactions that are known and established through experimental evidence are as follows:

- MKK2-MPK4
- MKK2-MPK2
- MKK4-MPK3
- MKK9-MPK3
- MKK1-MPK4
- MKK2-MPK6
- MKK5-MPK6
- MKK1-MPK11

These known interactions are presented in Table 2.3, which includes their associated functions according to the literature.

Computationally Predicted Interactions

The predicted interactions, which lack experimental evidence but were identified through computational methods, are as follows:

- MKK1-MPK1
- MKK1-MPK2
- MEKK1-MPK3
- YDA-MPK9
- MKK6-MPK13

- MEKK1-MPK17

These computationally predicted interactions are presented in Table 2.4, including their associated scores from STRING and ATTED-II.

Table 2.3 Experimentally Validated Upstream Interactions within the Selected Subset.

MPK	Interactor	Functions	References
MPK4	MKK2	Cold and Salt Stress Signaling, Represses Cell Death and Immune Responses	Kong et al. (2012); Teige et al. (2004)
MPK2	MKK2	Positive Regulation of Red Light-Induced Stomatal Opening	Li et al. (2023)
MPK3	MKK4	Agrobacterium-triggered Immunity, Agrobacterium-mediated Transformation	Liu et al. (2021)
MPK3	MKK9	Enhances Phosphate Acquisition, Ethylene and Camalexin Biosynthesis, Enhances Salt Stress Sensitivity	Lei et al. (2014); Xu et al. (2008)
MPK4	MKK1	Negatively Regulates Immunity	Kong et al. (2012)
MPK6	MKK2	Cold and Salt Stress Signaling	Teige et al. (2004)
MPK6	MKK5	ABA Regulation of Primary Root Growth, Stomatal Response	Li et al. (2017)
MPK11	MKK1	N/A	Lee et al. (2008b)

Table 2.4 Computationally Predicted Interactions within the Selected Subset.

MPK	Interactor	Sources	STRING Score	ATTED Logit Score
MPK1	MKK1	STRING, ATTED	0.693	3.344
MPK2	MKK1	STRING, ATTED	0.700	3.5388
MPK3	MEKK1	STRING, ATTED	0.705	3.6991
MPK9	YDA	STRING, ATTED	0.406	2.9775
MPK13	MKK6	STRING, ATTED	0.942	4.9706
MPK17	MEKK1	STRING, ATTED	0.459	3.0577

2.4 Discussion

2.4.1 Significance of the Integrated MPK Interaction Dataset

The integration of multiple sources of evidence, such as protein-protein interactions (PPIs), genetic interactions, and gene co-expression data, is crucial for exploring po-

tential interactions within the *Arabidopsis thaliana* MPK signaling network. This approach enhances the reliability and accuracy of predictions by providing a comprehensive understanding of the complex nature of cellular processes (Wu et al., 2010). By integrating diverse biological and computational sources of evidence, we can mitigate the limitations of individual data sources, such as high noise levels in high-throughput PPI data and inherent variability in gene expression profiles (Sriswasdi and Jensen, 2012; Tu et al., 2006).

The integrated dataset offers several advantages over single-data-source approaches. For instance, gene expression data can refine the topology of PPI networks by removing less relevant interactions, thereby simplifying the interactome for improved biological coherence (Sriswasdi and Jensen, 2012). Additionally, the condition-specific nature of PPIs suggests that integrating data on transcriptional regulation and gene expression can provide insights into the dynamic behavior of protein complexes under different environmental conditions (Luo et al., 2010). The integration of multiple sources of evidence compensates for the weaknesses of individual data types and provides a more robust framework for the prediction and analysis of PPIs and genetic interactions, leading to improved prediction coverage and accuracy (Li et al., 2012; Wu et al., 2010).

There are several potential applications of this dataset. By providing a comprehensive view of the *A. thaliana* MPK signaling network, this dataset can help address current research gaps, such as the characterization of uncharacterized MPKs and understanding of MAPKKK gene functions in plant stress responses. The integrated dataset can serve as a valuable resource for researchers investigating the roles of MPKs in various cellular processes and can guide future experimental studies aimed at validating predicted interactions and uncovering novel functional relationships within the MPK signaling network.

2.4.2 Characteristics of the Selected MPK Network Components

The selection of key MPK network components from the integrated dataset was based on the presence of multiple sources of evidence supporting each interaction. Interactions supported by all three sources of evidence (PPIs from STRING, genetic interactions from BioGRID, and gene co-expression from ATTED-II) were ranked highest, followed by those supported by two sources, and finally those supported by a single source. This ranking strategy allowed us to prioritize the interactions based on the strength

and consistency of the evidence supporting them, focusing on the most promising and reliable interactions for further investigation and validation.

The confidence scores associated with PPIs in the STRING database served as quantitative indicators of the strength of evidence for each predicted interaction. Higher scores suggest a greater likelihood of true biological significance, allowing for the prioritization of interactions for further investigation (Szkarczyk et al., 2011, 2019, 2023). Similarly, the logit score used in the ATTED-II database to measure gene co-expression provides a reliable assessment of the strength of co-expression between genes, with higher scores indicating stronger co-expression relationships (Obayashi et al., 2018, 2022). The combined co-expression platform, which integrates both microarray and RNA-Seq data, has been shown to have a higher function score than individual platforms, indicating better predictive performance (Obayashi et al., 2018, 2022).

Genetic interaction data from the BioGRID database was limited for *A. thaliana* MPKs, with only two interactions (MKK2-MPK4 and MKK2-MPK6) identified from the study by Teige et al. (2004). These interactions were categorized as "Synthetic Rescue," referring to the rescue of lethality or growth defects in a strain mutated/deleted for one gene by the mutation/deletion of another gene (Oughtred et al., 2020, 2018; Stark, 2006). The limited availability of genetic interaction data for MPKs in *A. thaliana* highlights the need for further experimental studies to uncover additional genetic relationships within the MPK signaling network.

The distribution of evidence types among the selected MPK network components has important implications for the reliability and biological relevance of the predicted interactions. Interactions supported by multiple sources of evidence are more likely to represent true functional relationships, as they have been consistently observed across different experimental and computational approaches. By focusing on these high-confidence interactions, we can identify the most essential and influential components of the MPK signaling network and guide future research efforts towards understanding their roles in plant stress responses and development.

2.4.3 Experimentally Validated Interactions and Biological Roles

In this exploratory study, we identified several experimentally validated interactions among selected interactions in *A. thaliana*. These interactions are supported by various experimental approaches that provide valuable insights into their functional roles and biological significance.

MKK2-Mediated Interactions and their Role in Cold and Salt Stress Signaling, Immunity, and Red Light-Induced Stomatal Opening

The interactions mediated by MKK2 are important for the regulation of stress signaling, immunity, and stomatal opening. Specifically, MKK2 activates MPK4, a process essential for the plant's response to cold and salt stress, as well as the negative regulation of plant immunity, which helps suppress unnecessary cell death and immune responses under normal conditions (Kong et al., 2012; Teige et al., 2004).

The MKK2-MPK2 interaction plays an important role in red light-induced stomatal opening, with MKK2 phosphorylating MPK2 in guard cells to trigger stomatal opening (Li et al., 2023). Additionally, MKK2's interaction with MPK6 contributes to the adaptation of plants to cold and salt stress (Teige et al., 2004), highlighting the diverse roles of MKK2 in various physiological processes.

MKK4 and MKK9-Mediated Interactions and their Role in Agrobacterium-Triggered Immunity, Phosphate Acquisition, and Stress Responses

The MKK4-MPK3 interaction is important for regulating plant immunity and transforming responses to *Agrobacterium* infection, inducing defense-responsive gene expression (Liu et al., 2021). The MKK9-MPK3 interaction enhances phosphate acquisition by regulating the transcription of phosphate-responsive genes and activates MPK3, influencing ethylene and camalexin biosynthesis as well as salt stress responses (Lei et al., 2014; Xu et al., 2008).

MKK1 and MKK5-Mediated Interactions and their Role in Suppressing Immunity and ABA-Regulated Root Growth and Stomatal Responses

The MKK1-MPK4 interaction is a key element of the MPK signaling cascade that suppresses immune responses to prevent autoimmunity (Kong et al., 2012). Additionally, the MKK5-MPK6 interaction, as part of the AIK1-MKK5-MPK6 cascade, plays a critical role in ABA regulation of root growth and stomatal responses, and is involved in regulating stomatal development, ethylene signaling, nitric oxide production, and hydrogen peroxide responses during plant growth and development (Li et al., 2017).

Limited Biological Significance of the MKK1-MPK11 Interaction

Although the physical interaction between MKK1 and MPK11 has been determined using yeast two-hybrid screening, the biological function of this interaction appears to be limited. *In vitro* phosphorylation assays showed very weak activity of MKK1 with

MPK11 as a substrate (Lee et al., 2008b), suggesting that the functional significance of this interaction may be less prominent than that of other validated interactions.

2.4.4 Computationally Predicted Interactions

The predicted MPK interactions exhibited varying levels of confidence, as indicated by their STRING and ATTED-II logit scores. The STRING scores ranged from 0.406 to 0.942, while the ATTED-II Logit scores ranged from 2.9775 to 4.9706. This set of predicted upstream MPK interaction partners forms the foundation for the functional and pathway enrichment analysis presented in Chapter 3.

Chapter 3

Functional Genomics Analysis of Predicted Interaction Genes

3.1 Introduction

Mitogen-activated protein kinase (MPK) signaling pathways in *Arabidopsis thaliana* are critical in regulating a wide range of cellular processes, however, the specific biological functions of some MPKs are yet to be determined [reference]. Additionally, the unclear functions of many MAPKKK genes prevent a complete understanding of MPK signaling pathways in stress responses [reference]. These knowledge gaps must be addressed to fully understand the complex regulatory mechanisms of the MPK signaling network.

To address these issues, functional genomic analysis methods were utilized to study the predicted MPK interaction genes identified in Chapter 2. The primary objective was to identify potentially shared functions among the interacting genes, thereby providing insights into complex regulatory mechanisms. An overrepresentation-based enrichment approach was used to identify significantly enriched biological processes, molecular functions, cellular components, and biological pathways associated with the predicted MPK interaction genes.

The findings from this functional genomics analysis are expected to contribute to a better understanding of the *A. thaliana* MPK signaling network and its role in plant stress responses and development. By identifying the significantly overrepresented functional and pathway terms among the predicted MPK interaction genes, this study aimed to provide a foundation for future experimental validation and further investigation into the complex regulatory mechanisms governing the MPK signaling network.

3.2 Materials and Methods

3.2.1 Fundamentals of Overrepresentation Analysis

For the functional genomics analysis of the selected MPK interactions, we used an overrepresentation-based enrichment approach. Overrepresentation Analysis (ORA) is a statistical method used to determine if a predefined set of genes is represented more than expected by chance within a specific category of genes, such as those belonging to a particular Gene Ontology (GO) term [reference]. ORA typically involves the use of a hypergeometric test or similar statistical methods to calculate the probability that the observed overlap between the query gene set and GO category occurs by random chance [reference].

3.2.2 Functional and Pathway Enrichment Analysis

g:Profiler (g:GOSt) Functional Enrichment Web Server

The functional and pathway enrichment analysis for the predicted MPK interaction genes from Chapter 2 was performed using g:Profiler (version e111_eg58_p18_30541362), a bioinformatics tool specifically designed for this purpose. g:Profiler allows for the identification of biological pathways that are significantly represented in a given list of genes or proteins [reference].

Using g:Profiler involves several steps, starting with the input of a gene list derived from either computational or experimental data. The algorithm then determines statistically enriched pathways by comparing the input list to known biological pathways and assessing the overrepresentation of pathways in the gene list more than would be expected by chance. The results can be visualized and interpreted to gain insights into the functional relationships underlying the query genes [reference].

Statistical Settings and Data Sources

The statistical domain scope was set to all annotated genes, and the significance method selected was g:SCS with a threshold of 0.05, which is the default method for multiple testing correction in g:Profiler. This helps with minimizing false-positive findings and ensuring reliable results [reference].

The Gene Ontology (GO) and Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes (KEGG) databases were selected as the data sources. For the GO data, the GO Molecular Function (GO:MF), GO Biological Process (GO:BP), and GO Cellular Component

(GO:CC) categories were selected. Additionally, electronic GO annotations were included in the enrichment analysis.

Table 3.1 Summary of g:Profiler Statistical Settings and Data Sources.

Settings	Specifications
Statistical Domain	All Annotated Genes
Significance Method	g:SCS (Multiple Testing Correction)
Significance Threshold	0.05
Data Sources	GO*, KEGG
GO Categories	GO:MF, GO:BP, GO:CC

Note. *Includes electronic GO annotations.

3.2.3 Visualization and Analysis

To visually represent the distribution of enriched terms for each category, a Manhattan plot was generated using g:Profiler. The Manhattan plot was used to provide a comprehensive overview of the enrichment results, with each point representing a specific term and its corresponding adjusted p-value. The x-axis represents the functional categories (GO, KEGG, and WP), while the y-axis represents the negative logarithm of the adjusted p-value. This plot was used to assess the overall enrichment results and identify the most significant functional categories and pathways related to the MPK interactome.

Considering that all input genes were components of the MPK network, it was anticipated that several widely recognized broad enrichments would emerge. However, to gain novel insights into the potential roles and mechanisms of the MPK interactome, it was essential to identify unexpectedly significantly enriched terms, as these unanticipated enrichments might suggest previously uncharacterized functions or regulatory pathways.

To better visualize and interpret these unexpected enrichments, a binary enrichment heatmap was generated using the ggplot2 package in R [reference]. The heatmap displays the presence or absence of significantly enriched terms across different functional categories (GO terms, KEGG pathways, and WikiPathways) for each input gene. The binary representation allows for a clear and concise visualization of the enrichment patterns, facilitating the identification of shared and unique functional associations among the MPK-related genes.

3.3 Results

The functional and pathway enrichment analysis of the predicted MPK interaction genes revealed a number of significantly enriched categories, consisting of GO terms and KEGG pathways. The Manhattan plot displayed in Figure 3.1 illustrates the distribution of the enrichment results.

Fig. 3.1 Manhattan Plot Illustrating the Functional and Pathway Enrichment Results.

Among the significantly enriched terms identified, many were anticipated based on prior knowledge. To focus the analysis on the most relevant and intriguing findings, terms that are particularly noteworthy were carefully selected. These selected terms of interest, along with their associated genes and adjusted p-values, are presented in Table 3.2.

Table 3.2 Selected Enriched Terms, Adjusted P-Values, and the Associated Genes.

Term Description	Adjusted P-Value	Genes
Response to L-glutamate	3.85×10^{-4}	MPK3, MEKK1
Response to wounding	1.01×10^{-3}	MPK2, MPK3, MKK1, MEKK1
Inflorescence development	1.76×10^{-2}	MPK3, YDA
Response to amino acid	2.59×10^{-2}	MPK3, MEKK1
Pollen-pistil interaction	2.78×10^{-2}	MPK3, MKK1
Post-embryonic plant morphogenesis	3.12×10^{-2}	MPK13, YDA, MKK6
Efferocytosis	4.79×10^{-2}	MPK13, MKK6

3.4 Discussion

3.4.1 MPK Signaling in Response to Nutrient Sensing

Our computational predictions have identified significant interactions within the MPK signaling pathways, particularly involving MPK3 and MEKK1 in the response to L-glutamate and amino acids. These results suggest a potential link between MPK signaling and the sensing or metabolism of these molecules. L-glutamate serves as a metabolic signaling molecule in plants, potentially activating the MEKK1-MPK3 signaling to influence nutrient sensing and signaling mechanisms compounds (Forde and Lea, 2007; Kan et al., 2017; McCoy et al., 2020).

3.4.2 MPK Pathways in Wound Response

The involvement of MPK2, MPK3, MKK1, and MEKK1 in response to wounding highlights a robust activation of MPK cascades following physical damage. This finding aligns with previous research, suggesting that MPK signaling is crucial for initiating hormonal signaling and transcriptional reprogramming during defense responses and tissue repair.

3.4.3 Developmental Roles of MPK Cascades

The MPK signaling network appears to play an important role in various developmental processes:

- **Inflorescence Development:** The association of MPK3 with YDA, and the involvement of the YDA-MPK9 module, might be related to their regulatory roles in cellular patterning and differentiation within floral tissues.
- **Post-Embryonic Plant Morphogenesis:** The interaction between MKK6 and MPK13, along with YDA, suggests a regulatory mechanism for growth and structural development after germination, essential for adapting to environmental conditions.

3.4.4 MPK Signaling in Reproductive Processes

Our analysis also indicates a role for MPK3 and MKK1 in pollen-pistil interactions, which are important for successful reproduction (Li et al., 2013). This interaction

may influence pollen tube growth and guidance, highlighting the integral role of MPK signaling in facilitating communication between pollen and pistil tissues.

3.4.5 Novel Roles in Plant Cell Death

Interestingly, the involvement of MPK13 and MKK6 in "efferocytosis" opens new avenues for research into the clearance of apoptotic cells, a relatively unexplored area in plant biology. This finding suggests a potential regulatory role for these kinases in managing plant cell death and survival.

Chapter 4

Predictive Modeling of MKK2 3D Structure with AlphaFold2

4.1 Introduction

4.2 Materials and Methods

4.2.1 AlphaFold2 and ColabFold

AlphaFold2

AlphaFold2 is a highly accurate deep learning algorithm developed to predict the three-dimensional (3D) structure of proteins from their amino acid sequences (Jumper et al., 2021; Ma et al., 2022). This algorithm has demonstrated remarkable accuracy in predicting protein structures, as evidenced by its success in the 14th Community Wide Experiment on the Critical Assessment of Techniques for Protein Structure Prediction (CASP14) (Takei and Ishida, 2022). The success of AlphaFold2 in predicting the 3D structures of single protein chains has raised questions about its future role in the field of protein structure prediction (Kwon et al., 2021).

One of the key advantages of AlphaFold2 is its ability to predict the 3D structures of proteins even when their native structures are unknown. This is achieved through the use of structure-based prediction methods, such as homology modeling or the application of AlphaFold2's deep learning capabilities (Pak and Ivankov, 2022). The neural network-based method of AlphaFold2 has allowed for the prediction of 3D structures for a significant portion of the human proteome, making these predicted structures publicly available (Zweckstetter, 2021).

ColabFold

ColabFold is an extension of AlphaFold2 that focuses on predicting protein complexes, offering both accuracy and speed in its predictions (Chang, 2023). By combining fast homology search with AlphaFold2 and RoseTTAFold, ColabFold can efficiently predict large protein complexes (Jussupow and Kaila, 2022, 2023). This implementation significantly reduces computation time, making it possible to predict protein-peptide complexes within a few minutes, depending on the system's size (Chang, 2023).

There have been various applications of ColabFold such as modeling protein structures and predicting changes in protein structure associated with genetic effects on traits and disorders (Einson et al., 2022; Hario, 2024; Rasjid, 2023). Additionally, ColabFold has been used to build complexes with specific peptides, demonstrating its versatility in various protein modeling tasks (Saliminasab, 2023; Zlobin et al., 2023).

4.2.2 MKK2 Structure Prediction and Visualization

In this study, we used the amino acid sequence of *Arabidopsis thaliana* MKK2 as a query in ColabFold to generate the top five ranked structural models. The top four models were subsequently selected for further analysis. For the identification of domains and functional sites, we used ScanProSite and InterProScan.

We used ChimeraX for the visualization and analysis of the protein models. Additionally, Root Mean Square Deviation (RMSD) values were calculated between different models to assess their structural divergence.

4.3 Results

AlphaFold2 was accessed through the ColabFold interface, where the amino acid sequence of MKK2 was inputted. This resulted in five top-ranking models, with the top four selected for further analysis. Various visualizations of these models are presented in Figure 4.1.

The analysis of the structural models revealed significant variations among the top four MKK2 models as indicated by Root Mean Square Deviation (RMSD) values. The RMSD between the first and second models was 6.470 Å, between the first and third models was 5.264 Å, and between the first and fourth models was 5.699 Å. Comparatively, the RMSD values between the second and third models, and between the second and fourth models were higher, at 8.112 Å and 7.624 Å, respectively, while the smallest deviation was observed between the third and fourth models at 3.565 Å.

Fig. 4.1 A) Top-ranked MKK2 model colour-coded by predicted Local Distance Difference Test (pLDDT) scores. (B) Superimposed structures of the MKK2 models, ranks 1-4. (C) Top-ranked MKK2 model with key functional sites labeled, identified using ScanProSite and InterProScan.

Functional site analysis predicted the presence of a protein kinase domain spanning residues 70 to 330, an ATP binding site across residues 76 to 99, and an active site between residues 188 to 200. These predictions highlight the critical regions potentially involved in the enzyme's catalytic function and substrate interactions.

4.4 Discussion

In regards to the structural variance among the MKK2 models, the RMSD values suggest that although there is a notable consistency between some models, significant disparities exist, especially between models two and three.

The functional site analysis reinforces the importance of specific residues in kinase activity and ATP binding, crucial for the protein's functional integrity. These structural insights are foundational for subsequent analyses where these four models are docked with MPK6, as detailed in Chapter 5. This docking study aims to analyze the interaction dynamics and the molecular mechanisms underlying the MKK2-MPK6 signaling pathway.

Chapter 5

In Silico Molecular Modeling of the MKK2-MPK6 Interface

5.1 Introduction

The MKK2-MPK6 interaction plays an important role in plant responses to cold and salt stress signaling. In this chapter, we explore the molecular basis of this interaction through in silico docking analysis using HADDOCK. This software enables us to model the protein-protein interface between MKK2 and MPK6, providing insight into how specific residues mediate their interaction. By understanding these molecular contacts, we aim to shed light on the structural underpinnings of the MKK2-MPK6 signaling mechanism.

5.2 Materials and Methods

5.2.1 Overview of HADDOCK

HADDOCK (High Ambiguity Driven protein-protein DOCKing) is a widely used software for predicting the three-dimensional structure of protein complexes, particularly in the context of protein-protein docking (?). It is a versatile tool that can be applied to model various biomolecular complexes and multi-component systems (?). HADDOCK utilizes experimental data, such as NMR Chemical Shift Perturbations and biochemical protein-peptide interaction data, as restraints to guide the docking process, making it an integrative modeling software (?). The docking in HADDOCK is driven by (experimental) knowledge in the form of information about the interface region between the molecular components and/or their relative orientations, making it applicable in

protein-ligand, protein-nucleic acid, and protein-protein docking predictions (Trellet et al., 2013). Furthermore, HADDOCK has been successful in selecting near-native docking poses in a variety of cases, including those of the CAPRI blind prediction experiment, demonstrating its efficacy in structure prediction (?).

5.2.2 Retrieval of MPK6's Structure from PDB

The experimental 3D structure of MPK6 (PDB ID: 6DTL) (Ruble, 2019) was originally determined through x-ray diffraction as reported by Putarjunan et al. (2019). To perform the protein-protein docking simulations of the MKK2-MPK6 interaction, we used HADDOCK which provides a data-driven method for modeling molecular complexes.

5.2.3 Protein-Protein Docking with HADDOCK

HADDOCK (High Ambiguity Driven protein-protein DOCKing) is a computational tool widely used for modeling protein-protein interactions. It specializes in utilizing experimental data such as NMR, mutagenesis, or bioinformatics predictions to drive the docking process by integrating biochemical and biophysical information. The strength of HADDOCK lies in its ability to handle ambiguous interaction restraints, allowing it to predict complexes with high accuracy even when precise details of the interaction are unknown (Dominguez et al., 2003). This makes it particularly useful in the study of complex biological mechanisms and the design of therapeutic molecules.

5.2.4 Visualization and Analysis

For visualization and analysis of the docking simulations, PyMOL was used to examine the interaction interfaces. This included a detailed investigation of bond types and interacting residues across each of the four simulations conducted.

5.3 Results

The outcomes of the docking simulations between MKK2 and MPK6 are presented, summarized in Table 5.1. Furthermore, a detailed 3D visualization of the MKK2-MPK6 interface is provided in Figure 5.1, highlighting the specific residues involved from both proteins.

Fig. 5.1 3D Visualization of the MKK2-MPK6 Interface for each MKK2 model being docked with MPK6, indicating the involved residues from both proteins.

Table 5.1 Summary of MKK2-MPK6 Docking Simulation Results.

	Binding Energy	Buried Surface Area	Desolvation Energy
#1	-475.02	3802.2	-7.71484
#2	-338.541	3796.74	-7.85969
#3	-445.666	3740.65	7.90779
#4	-318.102	4005.41	-14.3504

5.4 Discussion

5.4.1 Role of MKK2-MPK6 Interaction in Stress Signaling

The MKK2-MPK6 docking analysis reveals the critical residues and binding interfaces involved in this essential signaling pathway. The interaction sites identified suggest that these proteins form a stable complex that likely ensures efficient and accurate signal transmission. This reinforces the hypothesis that MKK2-MPK6 binding is a significant step in the activation of downstream stress response genes.

5.4.2 Implications for Plant Stress Resistance

The structural insights gained from this analysis could be instrumental in developing strategies for improving plant resilience. Understanding the specific residues involved in the MKK2-MPK6 interaction can help in the design of targeted mutations or small molecules that could enhance or disrupt this complex. This could be particularly useful for engineering plants with increased resistance to harsh environmental conditions.

5.4.3 Limitations and Future Research

Despite the comprehensive modeling approach, our docking analysis is limited by the static nature of in silico models. In vivo or in vitro studies are necessary to confirm the interaction dynamics and the role of specific residues identified in this study. Future research should focus on validating these findings through mutagenesis or protein interaction assays, as well as expanding the analysis to other related signaling pathways to uncover broader regulatory networks.

Chapter 6

Conclusion

The mitogen-activated protein kinase (MPK) signaling network plays a pivotal role in regulating plant stress responses and development. This thesis has employed a systematic and integrative approach to explore the complex interactions within the *Arabidopsis thaliana* MPK network. Through the integration of protein-protein interactions, genetic interactions, and gene co-expression data, a comprehensive dataset of potential MPK interactors was constructed and analyzed. This integrative strategy enhanced the reliability of predictions by leveraging multiple lines of evidence, compensating for the limitations of individual data sources.

The functional genomics analysis of the predicted MPK interactors revealed novel potential roles for MPK cascades in nutrient sensing, wound response, developmental processes, reproductive biology, and plant cell death regulation. Molecular modeling techniques, including AlphaFold2 for structure prediction and HADDOCK for protein-protein docking, provided valuable structural insights into the MKK2-MPK6 interaction interface. These findings contribute to our understanding of the intricate regulatory mechanisms underlying the MPK signaling network.

Furthermore, the knowledge gained from this research establishes a foundation for future experimental validation, mutagenesis studies, and the development of strategies to enhance plant stress tolerance. Ultimately, this thesis highlights the importance of integrating computational and experimental approaches in unraveling the complexities of biological systems, paving the way for innovative solutions in plant science and agriculture.

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Appendix A

Supplementary Materials

Potential Interactions of the 20 *Arabidopsis thaliana* MPKs

This table includes data on the potential interactions of the 20 *A. thaliana* MAPK (Mitogen-Activated Protein Kinases). The columns in the dataset represent the following variables:

- **MPK:** MPK identifier.
- **Interactor:** Identifier for the predicted interacting protein.
- **Num_Sources:** Number of sources supporting this predicted interaction.
- **Sources:** Source abbreviations where each letter represents:
 - **B:** BioGRID (genetic interaction evidence)
 - **S:** STRING (protein-protein interaction, known or predicted)
 - **A:** ATTED-II (gene co-expression data)
- **STRING_Score:** Confidence score for the interaction according to STRING.
- **ATTED_Logit_Score:** Logistic score representing gene co-expression levels.
- **BioGRID_Evidence_Type:** Type of genetic interaction evidence provided by BioGRID (if applicable).

The dataset is saved as a .csv file and can be accessed at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11113250>.

Gene Enrichment Map Data from gProfiler Analysis

This table contains data from the gene enrichment map analysis conducted with gProfiler on selected predicted interactions of MPKs. The columns in the dataset represent the following variables:

- **GO.ID:** Gene Ontology (GO) identifier.
- **Description:** Brief description of the GO term.
- **p.Val:** p-value from statistical testing.
- **FDR:** False discovery rate.
- **Genes:** List of genes associated with the GO term.

The dataset is saved as a `.txt` file and can be accessed at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11113422>.